

Evaluation of Error Vector Magnitude due to Combined IQ Imbalances and Phase Noise

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ABSTRACT

Novel closed form expressions for the Error Vector Magnitude (EVM) are presented. The expressions combine IQ amplitude and phase imbalances, DC offsets along with phase noise. Both the Gaussian and the Tikhonov probability density function are utilized for the oscillator phase noise distribution. The explicit conditions when EVM computations based on Tikhonov distribution converge to a Gaussian based are investigated. Furthermore, the application of the proposed EVM expressions is demonstrated by including phase noise masks, providing a direct means to Phase Locked Loop/Voltage Controlled Oscillator design parameters. Measurements are used to validate the proposed expressions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Error Vector Magnitude (EVM) is an important performance metric [1], [2] for RF transceivers used in high data rate wireless systems, such as WLAN and Digital Television. EVM can be derived numerically by system simulators [2], [3] and linked to other system parameters of interest such as the Bit Error Rate (BER) and Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) [2],[4]. There is great interest in closed form solutions which provide fast results and insight in terms of the sources of EVM degradation. EVM expressions that consider separately the effects of IQ amplitude imbalances, IQ phase imbalances and phase noise have been presented in [5]-[13]. In this work, the focus is on expressions that combine IQ amplitude, phase, DC offsets and phase noise in one closed formula.

Phase noise and IQ imbalances are limiting factors in chipset performance. However, only IQ amplitude and phase imbalances can be adaptively adjusted to low values [13-14]. The phase noise probability density function considered in previously reported EVM expressions was Gaussian ([2]-[13],[15]), suitable for low noise oscillator references. Phase noise in phase-locked loop (PLL) systems has been shown to satisfy the Tikhonov distribution [16][17][18]. The Tikhonov distribution is expected to converge to a Gaussian distribution at the low noise limit [18], [19]. These convergence limits for EVM have not yet been established. In this work, these limits are determined in the context of EVM by considering analytical formulas, for both Gaussian and Tikhonov phase noise probability density distributions.

In Section II, the general EVM formulation is outlined. Novel expressions based on combined phase noise and IQ amplitude, phase imbalances and DC offsets are derived in Section III for a Gaussian distribution. In Section IV, the Tikhonov distribution is discussed and novel EVM expressions for Tikhonov phase noise and IQ amplitude and phase imbalances are derived. The comparison between the two expressions is discussed in Section V in order to establish concrete

limits for the convergence. Validation of the proposed EVM expressions is given in Section VII based on the measurement set-up described in Section VI by taking advantage of phase noise masks. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VIII.

II. EVM Formulation

Consider a transmitter model using an IQ modulator and a Local Oscillator. A Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO) is necessary for multichannel operations such as Wifi systems and multiband cellular systems. A matrix system model is employed as in [5] (Fig. 1). An oscillator exhibiting a random phase noise φ_C can be represented as a matrix \mathbf{R} :

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi_C) & -\sin(\varphi_C) \\ \sin(\varphi_C) & \cos(\varphi_C) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Fig.1. System Structure under Additive Noise used for EVM evaluation.

The modulator matrix \mathbf{M} , for an amplitude imbalance g and phase imbalance φ , is expressed as [5]

$$\mathbf{M} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{1+g^2}} \begin{bmatrix} g \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) & \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \\ g \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The value 1 (in linear units) of the imbalance parameter g corresponds to no amplitude imbalances. Values of IQ amplitude imbalance up to 2 dB and phase imbalance of 5 degrees are typical upper limits in practice [14].

The squared rms value of EVM is derived in detail in [5] and only the result is repeated here for brevity,

$$EVM_{RMS}^2 = \frac{1}{SNR} + \frac{c^T c}{E_s} + 2 - Tr(H) \quad (3)$$

where:

$$H = R \cdot M \quad (4)$$

and

$$c = \sqrt{E_s} H \cdot a_{DC} \quad (5)$$

with a_{DC} is a column vector representing the effect of DC offsets in the modulator along the I and Q paths. $SNR = E_s/N_o$ is the system Signal-to-Noise Ratio due to thermal noise, with E_s the energy per symbol and N_o the noise spectral density. In (3), the symbol $Tr()$ represents the trace of the matrix and superscript T represents the transpose of the matrix. Expression (3) is independent of the constellation format as long as linear memoryless signals are transmitted. This is unlike BER which is in general different for each modulation scheme because of the use of the Q function which is related to the complementary Gaussian error function. It should also be noted that this squared rms EVM expression does not depend on the correlation properties of the noise vector [5].

Using (1) and (2) in (4), yields the matrix H , whose trace is

$$Tr(H) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{1+g^2}} \left[(1+g) \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \cos(\varphi_C) + (1-g) \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \sin(\varphi_C) \right] \quad (6)$$

The second term in (3), after some lengthy but straightforward matrix calculations, using the definition of (5) and under the assumption of identical DC offsets in the I and Q branches, yields

$$c^T c = E_s a_{DC}^2 \left[2 + \frac{4g}{1+g^2} \sin \varphi \right] \quad (7)$$

Using (6) and (7) in (3), the squared rms EVM due to the combined effect of phase noise, IQ amplitude, phase imbalances and DC offsets reads:

$$EVM_{RMS}^2 = \frac{1}{SNR} + a_{DC}^2 \left[2 + \frac{4g}{1+g^2} \sin \varphi \right] + 2 - \sqrt{\frac{2}{(1+g^2)}} \left[(1+g) \cos \frac{\phi}{2} \cos \phi_C - (1-g) \sin \frac{\phi}{2} \sin \phi_C \right] \quad (8)$$

Considering that phase noise is stochastic in nature, the squared rms value of EVM in (8) must be averaged over the corresponding probability density function (pdf) $\rho(\phi_C)$ with a phase noise variance σ .

$$EVM_{RMS,AVG}^2 = \int EVM_{RMS}^2 \rho(\phi_C) d\phi_C \quad (9)$$

III. GAUSSIAN PHASE NOISE AND IQ IMBALANCES

The local oscillator reference is commonly provided by a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL). The probability density function (pdf) of the PLL phase noise can be derived as the solution of a Fokker-Planck equation [18],[20]. In the limit of low noise variance σ , the pdf becomes Gaussian [18],

$$\rho_G(\phi_C) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\phi_C^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (10)$$

The integration of (8) over the Gaussian pdf (10) requires the integration of the third term which contains $\cos\phi_C$ and $\sin\phi_C$ terms. The integral containing the cosine term in (8) can be computed [5] using integral formulas from [21] whereas the sine term integral is zero due to the odd integrand. The average squared rms EVM eventually yields

$$EVM_{RMS,AVG}^2 = \frac{1}{SNR} + a_{DC}^2 \left[2 + \frac{4g}{1+g^2} \sin \varphi \right] + 2 - \sqrt{(1+\cos\varphi) \frac{(1+g)^2}{(1+g^2)}} \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) \quad (11)$$

By letting successively $\varphi=0^\circ$, $g=1$ (linear units), $\sigma=0^\circ$ and no DC offsets, expression (11) folds back to the separate EVM expressions presented for phase noise or imbalances only in [5]. It should be noted

that the combined expression (11) is not separable in phase noise terms or IQ imbalances (phase, amplitude, DC offset) only components.

IV. TIKHONOV PHASE NOISE DISTRIBUTION AND IQ IMBALANCES

A. The Tikhonov distribution

The Tikhonov distribution, also known as von Mises distribution is a generalized form of Gaussian distribution [16,17]. A common form of the Tikhonov distribution is given by

$$\rho_T(x; a, \xi) = \frac{1}{2\pi I_0(a)} \exp[a \cos(x - \xi)] \quad (12)$$

Where ξ is a centrality parameter, a is called concentration parameter, $I_0(a)$ is the modified Bessel function of order zero. Considering that the Tikhonov distribution function is also circular normal, the random variable x has a support length of 2π around ξ [17].

A form of the Tikhonov pdf (12) which is used in [18], [20], valid for sinusoidal PLL systems is given as

$$\rho_T(\phi_C) = \frac{\exp(a \cos \phi_C)}{2\pi I_0(a)} \quad (13)$$

with $-\pi \leq \phi_C \leq \pi$. The concentration parameter a intuitively corresponds to a PLL signal-to-noise metric defined for a linearized PLL model [18]. In (8), it is assumed that the VCO is tuned to the frequency of the reference oscillator and the problem consists only of acquiring and tracking the phase.

B. Average EVM

As in the case of Gaussian noise, average RMS expressions require integrating (8) over the Tikhonov pdf (13) using (9). Again, only the third term of (8), which contains $\cos\phi_C$ and $\sin\phi_C$ terms, requires averaging. The average value of the cosine of the phase noise under the Tikhonov distribution is given by

$$\overline{\cos(\phi_C)} = \frac{1}{2\pi I_0(a)} \int_{-\pi}^{+\pi} \cos(\phi_c) \rho_T(\phi_c) d\phi_c \quad (14)$$

The integration limits stem from the fact that the Tikhonov has support in $[\pi, -\pi]$.

A convenient form of (13) is a modified Bessel function series form given by [18]

$$\rho_T(\phi_c) = \frac{1}{2\pi I_0(a)} \left[I_0(a) + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} I_n(a) \cos n\phi_c \right] \quad (15)$$

where the symbol $I_n(a)$ denotes the modified Bessel function of n th order.

Using (15) in (14) and utilizing integral formulas from [21] yields

$$\overline{\cos(\phi_C)} = \frac{I_1(a)}{I_0(a)} \quad (16)$$

In a similar way, the average value of the sine of the phase noise is calculated as,

$$\overline{\sin(\phi_C)} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Taking into account (16) and (17), the averaged EVM for a combined Tikhonov phase noise and IQ imbalances situation reads,

$$EVM_{RMS,AVG}^2 = \frac{1}{SNR} + a_{DC}^2 \left[2 + \frac{4g}{1+g^2} \sin \varphi \right] + 2 - \frac{I_1(a)}{I_0(a)} \sqrt{\frac{(1+g)^2}{1+g^2} (1 + \cos \phi)} \quad (18)$$

The phase noise variance σ^2 is included implicitly in (18), as follows [18], [19]

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\pi^2}{3} + \frac{4}{I_0(a)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k^2} I_k(a) \quad (19)$$

It can be verified numerically that (19) is increasing strictly monotonically which leads to a one to one mapping between the phase noise variance σ and concentration parameter α . Therefore, based on

(18) and (19), $EVM_{RMS,AVG}^2$ is related to the phase noise variance by eliminating the parameter α . In

Fig.2 , the phase noise variance σ^2 is plotted against the concentration parameter α

Fig. 2 The Tikhonov phase noise variance as a function of the concentration parameter α

V. COMPARISON OF TIKHONOV AND GAUSSIAN BASED EVM

Comparing EVM expressions (11) and (18), it can be deduced that the difference depends on the ratio of the Bessel functions term and the exponential variance term. The two terms are plotted in Fig. 3 using (19) to provide the relationship between α and σ^2 . The plot is made for parameter α in the range 0 to 700, which corresponds to phase noise variance σ^2 in the range 5 to 350. The difference

becomes noticeable when $\frac{I_1(a)}{I_0(a)} < 0.45$ which occurs when the parameter α takes values less than

one.

Fig. 3 Comparison between the Gaussian and Tikhonov EVM factors

In order to establish a practical phase noise limit for EVM calculations, a plot of the ratio against the phase noise rms is plotted in Figure 4. From the plot, it is deduced that differences are generated for rms values of 26 degrees or more. Consequently for all practical cases, EVM can be calculated with either distribution.

Fig. 4 The ratio of Gaussian and Tikhonov EVM factors as a function of the rms phase noise.

VI. MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE

A. Phase noise masks

Measured phase noise masks have usually the shape of a piecewise linear characteristic [15]. The mask is extended from a frequency f_{min} up to a frequency f_{max} . (Fig.5).

It requires a frequency f_{OL} along with two noise power density levels, a plateau level, PL(dBc/Hz) and an overshoot level OL(dB) relative to the plateau level. The overshoot level which occurs at f_{OL} is utilized to account for the humps that may appear in PLL output spectra. The slope of the curve after f_{OL} is assumed to be -20dB/dec (thermal noise).

Fig.5. A phase noise mask model that represents the oscillator behavior.

The corresponding phase noise rms value σ can be evaluated based on this phase noise mask model by integrating the piecewise linear curve over the frequency domain

$$\sigma = \sqrt{2 \cdot 10^{\frac{PL}{10}} \left[f_{\min}^{-m} \left(\frac{f_{OL}^{1+m} - f_{\min}^{1+m}}{1+m} \right) + 10^{\frac{OL}{10}} f_{OL}^2 \left(\frac{1}{f_{OL}} - \frac{1}{f_{\max}} \right) \right]} \quad (20)$$

with m defined as a function of mask parameters,

$$m = \frac{OL}{10} \frac{1}{\log \frac{f_{OL}}{f_{\min}}} \quad (21)$$

In (20) a factor '2' was included to account for both noise sidebands assuming the spectral plot of Fig. 5 corresponds to one sideband around the carrier.

In Fig.6 the rms phase noise, as computed by (20), is plotted as a function of the plateau level, PL (dBc/Hz) for the case of $f_{\min}=1$ KHz, $f_{\max}=1$ MHz, $OL=0$ dB, $f_{OL}=100$ KHz. Thus a direct connection of mask parameters with EVM can be readily obtained.

Fig. 6 Phase noise rms value as a function of noise mask plateau level. Mask parameter values are $f_{min}=1\text{KHz}$, $f_{max}=1\text{MHz}$, $OL=0\text{dB}$, $f_{OL}=100\text{KHz}$.

B. EVM measurements

A measurement test bench was set up (Fig.7). The Agilent ESG 4438C Vector Signal Generator was used as a transmitter and the Agilent PSA E444A Spectrum Analyzer with Vector Signal Analysis (VSA) software was used as the receiver.

Fig.7. Set-up for EVM measurements

The EVM evaluation method presented here is independent of the modulation format. This is demonstrated by the use of two different modulation schemes as signals namely QPSK and 16-QAM.

The ESG transmitted a carrier signal of 2.45 GHz modulated using a 1MSPS signal and applying a Root Raised Cosine(RRC) filter with 0.35 roll-off factor. The PSA was used as a digital receiver and the VSA software was used to demodulate the digital radio signal and calculate the EVM in real time. It should be noted that VSA references EVM to the peak symbol energy whereas (11) and (18) use the average symbol energy. In order to compare the measured values for 16-QAM, a $\sqrt{9/5}$ factor is required [2][5].

IQ amplitude and phase imbalances are introduced by the built in option of the Signal Generator ESG 4438C. Phase noise was introduced to the transmitted signal by additionally using analog Phase Modulation with noise input at the ESG as the modulating signal. Effectively, this combination corresponds to a spectral profile similar to the one depicted in Fig. 5, with a flat plateau bandwidth of 100 KHz and no overshoot. Increasing the amount of phase deviation resulted in shifting the noise mask plateau to a higher value.

VII. VALIDATION OF COMBINED EVM EXPRESSIONS

For validation, the proposed EVM expressions are compared to measurements. Based on (11) the effects of phase noise on the EVM are plotted in Fig. 8. The combined effects of phase noise along with IQ amplitude and phase imbalances are plotted in Fig. 9 and Fig.10.

The EVM measurement corresponding to no amplitude, phase imbalance and phase noise was used to calculate an effective noise floor, which was evaluated to 47.6 dB. This SNR value was used in the theoretical calculations using (11).

Excellent agreement is observed in Fig.8 and Fig.9 regardless of the modulation format. The largest difference between measurements and the proposed expressions is less than 1% in EVM values.

Fig. 8 Measured and computed effects of the phase noise on the average rms value of EVM without IQ amplitude or phase imbalances. Both QPSK and 16-QAM Signals have been used in measurements. (SNR = 47.6 dB)

In Fig.10 typical upper limits of amplitude (2dB) and phase imbalances (5°) are considered with phase noise. The agreement is still very good for values up to 10° phase noise. For phase noise values larger than 10° , the proposed theory seems to overestimate EVM by 2%. This can be explained based on the way VSA operates. VSA computes the EVM by comparing each symbol to the nearest constellation symbol since the transmitted symbol information is not available [22], in contrast with the theoretical EVM calculation which is based on the comparison to a known transmitted symbol. This effectively results to smaller measured EVM values in the case where the error vector due to imbalances and noise is larger than the adjacent constellation symbol spacing [23].

Fig. 9 Combined effects of phase noise, IQ amplitude imbalance of $g=1\text{dB}$ and phase imbalance, $\varphi=1.5^\circ$ on the EVM. QPSK Signals have been used in measurements (SNR = 47.6 dB)

Fig. 10 Combined effects of phase noise and large IQ amplitude and phase imbalances. 16-QAM signals have been used in measurements (SNR = 47.6 dB)

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Novel analytical expressions were presented to account for the combined effect of phase noise, IQ amplitude and phase imbalances on EVM. The expressions are not separable in phase noise or amplitude and phases imbalances only contributions. The Tikhonov distribution was also utilized as a generalized phase noise model instead of the Gaussian distribution. It was shown analytically that for EVM calculations that using a Gaussian distribution as a phase noise model yields the same EVM results as the Tikhonov for all practical VCO phase noise values. Furthermore it was demonstrated how the proposed expressions can be linked to phase noise masks allowing designers to estimate

directly the impact of PLL parameters on the chipset EVM. The agreement with measurements for different digital modulation formats is very good.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A. Georgiadis was supported by EU Marie Curie FP7-PEOPLE-2009-IAPP 251557 and Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness project TEC 2012-39143.

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